

Set of Policy Documents for the ERIC

Deliverable D5.1

Estimated delivery date: 30/06/2025

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Funded by
the European Union

DOCUMENT DETAILS

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Document History

Version	Date	Change	Dissemination level
First version			
Second version			

Validation

Role	Reviewer	Validation Date
Task Leader	Sarah Essam Taha	
Reviewers	EU-Solaris GA members	
Project's consortium		
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Distribution List

Date	Recipients
	All members of the SOLARIZE Consortium and the Commission services

Disclaimer

SOLARIZE project is funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement No 101131982.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines the implementation of the EU-SOLARIS ERIC governance structure, detailing the operational framework, decision-making bodies, and internal policies that underpin the consortium's legal and strategic functions.

EU-SOLARIS was established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in 2022 to coordinate, integrate, and provide access to high-quality Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) and Solar Thermal Energy (STE) research infrastructures across Europe. As a distributed infrastructure governed by the ERIC legal framework, EU-SOLARIS is committed to excellence, transparency, and alignment with European Research Area (ERA) priorities.

The governance model is anchored in the Statutes and is operationalized through a well-defined structure comprising the General Assembly (as the supreme decision-making body), the Managing Director (responsible for day-to-day operations), the Scientific & Technical Committee (STC), and the Board of National Nodes (BNN). Each body contributes to a coherent decision-making process that ensures scientific merit, national coordination, and policy implementation.

To support its mission, EU-SOLARIS ERIC has adopted a suite of policies which guide internal and external operations. These include:

- The **Access Policy**, enabling fair and transparent user access based on scientific excellence and technical feasibility;
- The **Human Resources Policy**, promoting merit-based recruitment and equal opportunity;
- The **Procurement and Tendering Policy**, ensuring non-discriminatory, competitive procurement in line with EU regulations;
- The **Intellectual Property and Inventions Policy**, clarifying rights over generated knowledge and ensuring fair use of background IP;

Additionally, EU-SOLARIS has articulated its forward-looking vision in the **Strategic Plan 2023–2026**, which defines institutional priorities, user engagement, infrastructure integration, and service development. Progress toward these goals is continuously monitored through defined

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), reported annually to the General Assembly.

The implementation of governance is structured around two operational layers: (1) core activities funded through member contributions, including access coordination, policy management, and standardization; and (2) supplementary activities supported through competitive external projects, such as e-infrastructure development and training.

This deliverable demonstrates that EU-SOLARIS ERIC has successfully transitioned from legal establishment to functional implementation, with the institutional structures, policies, and strategic planning in place to ensure sustainability, openness, and European leadership in solar thermal research and innovation.

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Table of acronyms

Acronym	Full Form
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
GA	General Assembly
DMS	Document Management System
STC	Scientific and Technical Committee
CST	Concentrated Solar Thermal
DLR	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e. V. (German-Aerospace-Center)
PROMES-CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique – PROMES
CIEMAT-PSA	Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas – Plataforma Solar de Almería
NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory
CYI	The Cyprus Institute
LNEG	Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia
IMDEA	Instituto Madrileño de Estudios Avanzados
QA	Quality Assurance
BNN	Board of National Nodes
CSP/STE	Concentrating Solar Power / Solar Thermal Energy
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
GA	General Assembly
IPR	Intellectual property rights
MD	Managing Director
RI	Research Infrastructure
STC	Scientific & Technical Committee
SLA	Service Level Agreement

1 Governance Structure & Legal Entity

- **Statutory Establishment (ERIC)**

EU-SOLARIS ERIC legally came into being in **October 2022**, following the formal establishment by the European Commission. It constitutes a **non-profit pan-European consortium** headquartered at the Plataforma Solar de Almería, Spain, with Members (Germany, France, Cyprus, Spain) and Portugal, Greece as Observers.

- **Governing Bodies**

- **General Assembly:** Supreme authority, composed of official representatives from Members and Observers; responsible for overarching strategic decisions and approval of ERIC policies.
- **Managing Director:** Appointed by the General Assembly; legal representative and chief executive in charge of daily operations.
- **Scientific & Technical Committee (STC):** Advises the General Assembly, evaluates scientific outputs, and recommends technical improvements.
- **Board of National Nodes (BNN):** Coordinates with national infrastructure nodes to ensure coherence across Member States

2 Core Policies & Their Implementation

2.1 Access Policy

Reference: ([Access Policy, Nov 2023](#))

The EU-SOLARIS ERIC Access Policy provides the framework through which researchers and users may gain access to the distributed research infrastructures and services offered by the consortium. Its purpose is to ensure transparent, fair, and scientifically driven access procedures, in alignment with the objectives and legal obligations set out in the EU-SOLARIS ERIC Statutes.

General Principles

According to Article 23 of the Statutes, EU-SOLARIS ERIC promotes access that:

- Is based on scientific merit and technical feasibility;
- Supports excellence in solar thermal research;
- Encourages user training and practical engagement with experimental facilities;
- Respects the principles outlined in the **European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures**.

Access is open to **all user types**, including researchers, engineers, industry representatives, and public or private stakeholders from both European and non-European countries. However, such access **is not necessarily free of charge** and may be subject to cost-recovery principles depending on user type, facility, and scope of service.

Access Modalities and Procedures

Requests for access are managed through a **streamlined process** involving:

- **Eligibility and feasibility checks**;
- **Scientific peer review**, where applicable;
- Evaluation against predefined criteria established by the **Managing Director**, in consultation with the **Scientific & Technical Committee (STC)** and the **Board of National Nodes (BNN)**;
- Final approval by the **General Assembly**.

All **procedures, criteria, and access costs** are clearly documented and publicly available on the EU-SOLARIS ERIC website to guarantee transparency and equal treatment of applicants.

Rights, Ethics, and Responsibilities

The policy ensures that access is granted in a manner that:

- **Honours the rights and responsibilities of facility owners**, including those related to data privacy, IPR, safety, and ethics;
- **Protects user confidentiality**, both during evaluation and throughout the research process;
- **Requires users** to fully comply with security protocols and institutional access conditions;
- Respects the proprietary nature of certain data, equipment, or outcomes linked to individual research centres.

All access activities are **aligned with the ethical, legal, and technical obligations** of EU-SOLARIS ERIC Members, and users must agree to these terms through formalised access agreements.

Operational Legacy and Best Practices

The implementation of this Access Policy builds on **extensive experience** developed during earlier European initiatives such as **SFERA, SFERA II, and SFERA III**, which pioneered harmonised access procedures for solar research infrastructures. The lessons learned from these projects have been integrated into the current EU-SOLARIS ERIC model to ensure continuity, quality, and compliance with European best practices.

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2.2 Human Resources Policy

Reference: [EU-SOLARIS ERIC HR Policy \(June 2024\)](#).

The EU-SOLARIS ERIC Human Resources Policy sets the framework for fair, transparent, and inclusive personnel management aligned with the ERIC's mission as a pan-European research infrastructure. It ensures that all employment practices adhere to European legal standards and ethical principles.

Core Principles

The HR Policy is based on:

- **Non-discrimination and equal opportunity**, regardless of gender, ethnicity, religion, disability, or political beliefs;
- **Merit-based recruitment**, with open and transparent selection processes;
- **Staff development**, including training, upskilling, and knowledge-sharing opportunities;
- **Workplace integrity and safety**, promoting respectful and healthy working environments.

EU-SOLARIS ERIC aims to attract and retain highly qualified personnel through competitive hiring, long-term career planning, and professional growth pathways. The policy reinforces the ERIC's commitment to the **European Charter for Researchers** and the **Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers**.

Employment Categories and Governance

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The policy applies to:

- Core administrative and management staff;
- Researchers and technical experts employed directly or seconded from Member institutions;
- Temporary and project-based personnel.

All employment decisions are made under the oversight of the **Managing Director**, in consultation with the **General Assembly**, with mechanisms for feedback and redress in case of conflict or grievance.

2.3 Procurement & Tendering Policy

Purpose & Scope

Reference: ([Procurement & Tendering Policy](#)).

The Procurement & Tendering Policy provides the internal framework for EU-SOLARIS ERIC to conduct purchasing in a manner that is transparent, fair, competitive, and non-discriminatory as required by ERIC Statutes and EU law.

Key Principales

- Procurements must comply with **transparency, equal treatment, and integrity** principles, regardless of whether suppliers are from Member or non-Member States.
- The policy explicitly prohibits the intentional splitting of procurements to avoid competition or procurement thresholds, ensuring **value for money** and fair market access.

Governance & Internal Oversight

- The **Managing Director** is responsible for drafting internal procurement regulations and criteria, which must be approved by the **General Assembly**.
- The Managing Director oversees the tendering process, guided by the protocols approved in internal regulations.

Procurement Procedures

- **Publication of opportunities:** All calls for tender and award decisions are published on the EU-SOLARIS ERIC website, with detailed justification of contract awards.
- **Valuation thresholds:**
 - Contracts under defined low-value thresholds may proceed with **limited competition** (e.g. quotations from at least three suppliers).
 - Higher-value contracts require **formal tendering processes**, including open calls or restricted procedures in line with rules established in internal regulations.

Supplier Obligations & Integrity Measures

- Suppliers must be treated impartially, and potential **conflicts of interest** are actively managed to prevent undue influence or unfair advantage.
- Tender documents and evaluations are structured to ensure **competition, transparency, and accountability** in award decisions.

Appeals & Audit Procedures

- Though not detailed in the public summary, internal regulations may establish mechanisms for **appeals or dispute resolution**, and audits to ensure policy compliance.
- Many ERIC frameworks adopt audit review, appeals boards, and internal audit provisions to safeguard procurement integrity—a template consistent with broader ERIC practice.

2.4 Intellectual Property & Inventions Policy

Reference: ([Intellectual Property & Inventions Policy](#)).

The EU-SOLARIS ERIC Intellectual Property & Inventions Policy establishes a structured approach to managing ownership, access, and use of intellectual property rights (IPR) generated within its distributed research infrastructure. It supports a balance between open access principles and the protection of proprietary knowledge

Foundational Principles

- EU-SOLARIS ERIC aligns with the principles of **transparency, open science**, and **responsible IPR management**.
- IPR generated by EU-SOLARIS ERIC's internal activities will, by default, be owned by the ERIC.
- Users retain ownership of their project-generated IPR, while background IPR introduced by any party remains with the original holder.
- Limited ownership or usage rights may be granted to users for a defined time, particularly in relation to data generated with EU-SOLARIS ERIC infrastructure.
- The policy respects **national legislation**, applicable international treaties, and any specific bilateral agreements between the ERIC and its Members or Observers.

Key Definitions

The policy defines:

- **Background IPR:** Pre-existing intellectual property introduced into a research project.
- **Foreground IPR:** New intellectual property resulting from project activity based on the background IPR.
- **Project IPR:** Any intellectual property developed during the execution of a research project using EU-SOLARIS ERIC infrastructure.
- **Executing Party / Disclosing Party / Receiving Party:** Stakeholders involved in the transfer or handling of confidential information and IPR across research activities.

Disclosure & Confidentiality

- All project results from non-commercial research are encouraged to be openly shared, while ensuring protection of IPR.
- Users must acknowledge the use of EU-SOLARIS ERIC resources in any publications.
- Confidential project information must be safeguarded through NDAs and internal handling protocols, with a confidentiality obligation of up to five (5) years.

Ownership and Use of Background IPR

- Background IPR remains fully owned by the originating party.
- Users may request a **non-exclusive, royalty-free license** for academic use. For commercial exploitation, fair market terms apply.
- Any inseparable improvements to background IPR are also considered part of the original property.

Ownership and Use of Project IPR

- Users own the IPR generated in their projects, with obligations to:
 - Declare potential IPR conflicts;
 - Share royalties if their work commercially exploits another user's protected contribution;
 - Respect the funder's conditions (e.g., under EU grants, Horizon Europe).

Conflict Resolution and Amendments

- Disputes over IPR ownership or usage are to be resolved through **arbitration** under Spanish law.
- The General Assembly may revise the policy without prior notice; any updates are published on the official website.
- Questions of interpretation are addressed by the EU-SOLARIS Central Hub.

Governance Integration

This policy ensures alignment with:

- The Access Policy (regarding user data and access-related rights);
- The Data Policy (FAIR/open access frameworks);
- The Statutes (Article 10.5), making the General Assembly the formal authority on approval.

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2.5 Other Policies (Data, Ethics & Dissemination)

Reference: ([EU-SOLARIS ERIC Other Policies- December 2024](#)).

These policies establish an integrated governance framework concerning data management, dissemination, scientific evaluation, and ethics, fully aligned with the statutory requirements of EU-SOLARIS ERIC

Scientific Evaluation Policy

- Purpose: Ensures fair, transparent, and impartial peer review of all access applications.
- Evaluation criteria include scientific merit, sector needs, and potential impact.
- The process is defined in internal regulations developed by the Managing Director in consultation with the STC and BNN and approved by the General Assembly.

Dissemination Policy

- Objective: Maximize visibility and uptake of research conducted through EU-SOLARIS ERIC.
- Users are required to publicly disseminate results—respecting confidentiality and IPR—via EU-SOLARIS channels.
- Target audiences include scientific communities, policymakers, industry stakeholders, and the general public.

Data Policy

- Framework: Based on FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) and open access ethos.
- The Managing Director proposes internal regulations on data governance, including:
 - User compliance obligations,
 - Security protocols,
 - Breach investigation procedures,
 - Privacy protection.
- These are reviewed and approved by the General Assembly.

Ethics & Confidentiality

- All policies reinforce compliance with ethical standards, confidentiality agreements, and good scientific conduct.
- Users must respect property rights, confidentiality, and security measures defined by the participating research centers.
- Ethical compliance is monitored throughout the access and evaluation process, ensuring integrity in research activities.

2.6 Strategic Plan 2023–2026

Reference: [GO-06 Strategic Plan 2023–2026 – Update December 2024 \(PDF\)](#)

The Strategic Plan defines the institutional roadmap for EU-SOLARIS ERIC, emphasizing its role as a pan-European reference infrastructure in Concentrated Solar Power and Solar Thermal Energy (CSP/STE). The updated 2024 version articulates six high-level strategic objectives:

1. **Integration & Coordination:** Unify CSP/STE infrastructure access across Member States through central coordination and interoperable standards.

2. **Service Provision & User Support:** Develop a common access platform, harmonized procedures, and tailored user support to improve scientific productivity.
3. **Industry Engagement & Innovation:** Foster R&D collaboration with industrial partners to accelerate technology transfer and commercial deployment.
4. **Training & Human Capital:** Promote capacity building through mobility programs, staff exchanges, technical training, and seasonal schools.
5. **Scientific Leadership & Visibility:** Consolidate EU-SOLARIS's role as a leading actor in CSP/STE by contributing to European research agendas, standardization, and public outreach.
6. **Sustainability & Governance:** Ensure long-term operational sustainability through strong governance, diversified funding, and strategic alignment with ESFRI and EU Green Deal goals.

The Plan is structured into action lines with milestones and is operationalized by the Central Hub and National Nodes under General Assembly oversight.

2.7 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Reference: [OD-6 Key Performance Indicators – May 2025 \(PDF\)](#)

The KPIs framework supports both internal performance monitoring and external accountability to ESFRI and REA. Eighteen KPIs have been selected by the Central Hub across six strategic dimensions:

Objective	Example KPIs
Enabling Scientific Excellence	Publications, access requests, international user reach
Operational Performance	Facility utilization, user satisfaction
Capacity Building & Knowledge	Staff exchanges, training events, industry participation
Societal & Environmental Impact	Outreach events, dissemination channels
Optimizing Management	Staff training hours, budget variance
Financial Sustainability	External funding, governance compliance

Each KPI includes a methodology, frequency, and reporting responsibility. They are aligned with ESFRI RACER standards and support both annual self-assessment and the 5-year ESFRI Landmark monitoring cycle.

3 Implementation Model & Delivery Plan

- **Operating Layers:**
 - **Core Activities** (funded via member contributions): access facilitation, standardization, user mobility, facility coordination, staff exchanges, platform liaison with European institutions.
 - **Supplementary Projects** (external funding): development of an e-infrastructure, new facility support if needed, ongoing training (e.g. summer school), standard protocols, and international collaboration initial.
- **Timeline:**
 - **Q4 2022:** Establishment of ERIC and governance bodies.
 - **Early 2023:** Launch of centralized access operations and user evaluation processes.
 - **2023–2026:** Phased implementation of strategic objectives and KPI-linked monitoring.

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4 Governance Implementation Matrix

Governance Domain	Responsible Bodies	Implementation Mechanism
General oversight	General Assembly	Policies ratified; strategic direction finalized
Executive management	Managing Director & Central Office	Day-to-day operations, policy enforcement, coordination across facilities
Technical evaluation	Scientific & Technical Committee (STC)	Evaluation of access proposals; reviews of scientific merit and alignment with sector needs
National coordination	Board of National Nodes (BNN)	Ensures alignment between Member State infrastructure nodes and EU-SOLARIS strategy

Governance Domain	Responsible Bodies	Implementation Mechanism
Policy deployment	STC, BNN, MD, GA	Drafting by MD → consultation with STC/BNN → final approval by General Assembly
KPI tracking	Managing Director & Secretariat	Data collection, indicator tracking, analysis, and reporting to GA
Policy approval	General Assembly	Ratifies all official ERIC policies, budget allocations, appointments, and strategic documents
Policy execution	Managing Director	Executes GA decisions, oversees staff, contracts, and service-level implementation
Scientific oversight	Scientific & Technical Committee	Reviews access proposals, advises on R&D priorities, and ensures technical excellence
Facility integration	Board of National Nodes	Coordinates national infrastructures, harmonizes access processes, supports mobility and training programs

Terms of Reference – Governance Bodies of EU-SOLARIS ERIC

Body	Appointment & Term	Core Responsibilities
General Assembly (GA)¹	Composed of representatives from Members and Observers. Chair and Vice-Chair elected for 3 years (renewable once). Meets at least twice a year.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supreme governing body of the ERIC. - Approves policies, strategy, budget, and annual reports. - Appoints/dismisses the Managing Director, STC and BNN members. - Decides on membership, financial contributions, and statutory changes.

¹ [Internal Regulations of the General Assembly](#)

Body	Appointment & Term	Core Responsibilities
Managing Director (MD) ²	Appointed by the General Assembly for a 5-year term, renewable once.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chief executive and legal representative of the ERIC. - Implements GA decisions. - Prepares budget, work plan, strategic plan, and annual reports. - Drafts internal policies and coordinates access, funding, and risk management.
Scientific & Technical Committee (STC) ³	Members appointed by the General Assembly for up to 4 years, renewable.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Advises on scientific and technical matters. - Reviews access proposals and scientific quality. - Evaluates R&D performance. - Makes recommendations on infrastructure and strategic development.
Board of National Nodes (BNN) ⁴	One representative per Member State infrastructure. Chaired by the Managing Director (non-voting).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinates implementation of strategies across national nodes. - Aligns access procedures, operations, and technical standards. - Provides input on mobility, training, and infrastructure interoperability.

5 Key Risk & Quality Control

- **Risk Assessment:** While D5.2 is the formal risk plan, governance implementation includes mitigation against non-compliance, access misuse, inconsistent procurement, privacy breaches, or IP disputes.
- **Quality Assurance:** Internal and external audits will be scheduled; the General Assembly will receive annual quality and policy compliance reports.

² [Terms of Reference Managing Director](#)

³ [Terms of Reference Scientific & Technical Committee](#)

⁴ [Terms of Reference Board of National Nodes](#)

6 Overall Summary

Deliverable D5.1 documents how EU-SOLARIS ERIC implements its governance via structured bodies (General Assembly, MD, STC, BNN), applies core policies (Access, HR, Procurement, IPR, Data, Ethics), and operationalizes its Strategic Plan (2023–2026) supported by KPI monitoring. The two-tier model (core funded activities plus external-funded projects) ensures capability-building, policy consistency, and alignment with European Research Area objectives.